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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
AI	Artificial intelligence (AI) is the ability of a computer or a robot controlled by a computer to do tasks that are usually done by humans because they require human intelligence and discernment
BIM	Building Information Modelling is a digital representation of physical and functional characteristics of a facility.
Citizen Participation	Citizen participation' refers to citizen involvement in public decision making. In different interpretations, 'citizens' may be either individuals or organized communities, and 'participation' may involve either observation or power.
NEB	The New European Bauhaus is a creative and interdisciplinary initiative that connects the European Green Deal to our living spaces and experiences.
Open-source software	Software that is released under a license in which the copyright holder grants users the rights to use, study, change, and distribute the software and its source code to anyone and for any purpose
Parametric design	A design method in which features, such as building elements and engineering components, are shaped based on algorithmic processes rather than direct manipulation

Keywords

New European Bauhaus; Digital Projects; Digital Solutions; Landscape Analysis, Gap Analysis.

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Executive Summary

DigiNEB.eu investigates digital innovations available for wider adoption within the New European Bauhaus (NEB) community to achieve its ambitious goals. Within this scope, DigiNEB places special emphasis on digital innovations stemming from various European research programs, as well as those shared through open-source channels.

This report is crafted within this framework, aiming to provide an overview of the landscape while simultaneously conducting a gap analysis. By compiling the initial overview of more than 250 digital tools for the NEB community, we became aware of several prominent clusters of projects and tools:

- EU consortia working on BIM solutions/Digital Twins;
- Individuals or small groups working on plugins for parametric design applications such as Rhino and Grasshopper;
- Providers of citizen engagement tools, often civic organizations, foundations, cooperatives, and local/regional authorities;
- Tools and project focussing on training and skills;
- AI start-ups and services.

The report discusses these clusters one by one, highlighting one example of each with the main characteristics for the purpose of a comparison and gap analysis. The initial analysis identifies six main gaps dealing with: i) Funding; ii) Accessibility; iii) Findability; iv) Integration, v) Interoperability, vi) Reusability.

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1. Introduction

DigiNEB.eu investigates digital innovations available for wider adoption within the New European Bauhaus (NEB) community to achieve its ambitious goals. Within this scope, DigiNEB will create and deliver a set of support services that work around four principal pillars: i) creating an active network between digital and NEB communities, engaging and facilitating cooperation and co-creation between cross-domain stakeholders through events, network building and development; ii) mapping and showcasing existing digital solutions, projects and tools (especially capitalising on those funded through EU programmes); iii) producing capacity building material to support the update of identified best practice uses of digital technologies for the NEB objectives and iv) issuing recommendations and a *NEB Digital Deployment Roadmap* to address current gaps in the development of digital solutions for NEB.

This report is crafted within this framework, aiming to provide an overview of the landscape of solutions, projects and tools while simultaneously conducting a gap analysis. Both of these actions are tied to the NEB initiative, inherently addressing its core values: beauty (aesthetics), sustainability, and together (inclusivity).

- **Aesthetics** encompass all elements related to form, size, texture, color, proportion, space, culture, context, history, heritage, and more.
- **Sustainability** encompasses efforts towards aspects such as energy efficiency, climate adaptation and mitigation, circularity, and ecology.
- **Inclusivity** can be understood through the lenses of universal design, citizen participation, participatory planning, health and well-being, democratization, and community engagement.

These categories are not rigidly separated. We've encountered several instances of overlap, finding that some digital solutions fit into multiple categories. In fact, integrating the three objectives is an overall aim of the NEB.

It should be noted that our analysis has primarily focused on architecture, urbanism, and the broader built environment. Nevertheless, crossovers are often evident. There are connections with product design, industrial design engineering, gaming, visual culture, graphic design, typography, video, and art on one hand, and construction, engineering, transportation, and energy on the other.

Given the nature of our analysis, our focus should primarily centre around the creative aspects of the NEB landscape: ideation, design, construction, and production. However, when considering the economic and cultural dimensions of this landscape, it is important to delve deeper into innovations that support small and medium enterprises (SMEs), including micro enterprises. This may include activities like bookkeeping, tendering, recruiting, and communication. For the future generation of designers, providing training, education, and facilitating knowledge dissemination and debates are crucial as well. The ability for the end-user to create functional custom “solution contexts portfolios” will increase because sustainable building assets design will have to prepare for innovations in other more technical areas as well: one example for illustration is management of water/waste water/energy storage also in larger building assets fleets.

While there is a wide variety of digital tools available, we especially look to tools developed in EU-funded projects, open-source tools, and community tools. Standard commercially available tools like those of Autodesk or Adobe are not included. Within the initial collection of over 250 projects and tools identified, four main clusters can be observed: parametric design tools, Building Information Modelling (BIM) and digital twins, citizen engagement platforms, and an emerging and fast-developing cluster of artificial intelligent services (AI). We will address these separately and provide examples for each of them.

2. Method

We began by identifying the web sources that catalogue various groups of projects and digital tools relevant to the NEB community. To name some of the more prominent sources:

- **European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP)** • <https://dbe.ectp.org>
- **food4Rhino** • <https://www.food4rhino.com/en/browse>
- **Parametric House** • <https://parametrichouse.com>
- **Democracy Technologies** • <https://democracy-technologies.org/database/>
- **YouTube and Instagram** (AI tools)
- **RISE** • <https://www.ri.se/en/what-we-do>
- **dara.digital** • <https://www.dara.digital>
- **digital built Britain** • <https://www.cdbb.cam.ac.uk/research/digital-built-environment>

We have summarised and categorised these tools on the DigiNEB web portal, where selected descriptions and images from the developers were merged with links to the original web sources of the projects and toolsets. In this way we were able to prepare 250+ tools and projects available for evaluation and investigation, using a comparative abstraction level. The tools were then clustered:

- 60 Parametric design
- 27 Community
- 25 Training/Skills
- 21 BIM/Digital Twins
- 19 Energy
- 18 Data/Digital/Monitoring
- 14 Retrofitting/circular
- 14 Smart/IoT
- 14 Urban/Rural
- 09 AI
- 09 Platforms/Network
- 15 Miscellaneous

Note: The category of parametric design tools is topic-wise heterogeneous and comprises tools for i.e., energy or data analysis. Some tools overlap two clusters but were not double listed. They were assigned to one cluster only.

3. Input for the Technical Working Groups (TWGs)

From these clusters we derive four main thematic groups within the NEB community, and one fifth integration level group:

- Parametric design (with EAAE/ACE)
- Education, training, skills development (with EAAE)
- Community engagement with cities, regions, foundations (with ICF)
- BIM/Digital Twins (with ECTP)
- Biobased materials and solutions as cross-domain integrator (with Innovawood/ACE)

The aim of the TWGs is to identify solutions that did not surface during the initial tool/project identification process and to broaden the potential field of digital innovation beyond the core 'creative' focus of the NEB community.

The activity is scheduled for months 13-24 and will inform the final landscape and gap analysis (D2.5).

This D2.3 report concerns the preliminary analysis over months 1-12.

A focus for the next step could include important application areas beyond design:

- Tendering, recruiting, archiving and communication;
- Solutions that involve several clusters and additional ones over time in the total work situation, allowing users to create their own unique functional work context (work bench combining tools etc);
- Platforms that enable construction professionals to collaborate on projects from any connected device with access to all project documents, contracts, RFIs, submittals, schedules, drawings and more like for instance VOLUM3;
- Material Passports / Advanced Materials (with ICF/BEDA);
- Management of waste water - capturing the nutrients in waste water.

4. The Landscape of Digital Tool Development for NEB

By compiling the initial overview of more than 250 digital tools for the NEB community, we became aware of several prominent clusters. In this report we discuss five of those that allow us to provide a rough sketch of the landscape:

- EU consortia working on BIM solutions/Digital Twins;
- Individuals or small groups working on plugins for parametric design applications such as Rhino and Grasshopper;
- Providers of citizen engagement tools (often civic organizations, foundations, cooperatives, local/regional authorities);
- Tools and project focussing on training and skills;

And a fast-moving new category:

- AI start-ups and services.

Although the cluster of training/skills is substantial in numbers, the cluster is less cohesive and not that easy to illustrate with a single or view case studies or examples.

In the next paragraphs we will discuss the clusters one by one, presenting one example for each cluster and highlighting their main characteristics for the purpose of comparison and gap analysis.

4.1 EU Consortia on BIM Solutions and Digital Twins

The *European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP)* serves as an excellent starting point for identifying digital projects funded by the EU in the construction sector and various other sectors within the built environment supply chain. The largest subgroup of projects focuses on Building Information Modelling (BIM) and Digital Twins. Additionally, Topics focussed on are: tool development related to energy, retrofitting/circularity, and data/digital monitoring. These consortia typically comprise participants who, owing to their size and capabilities, are well-equipped to engage in Horizon calls.

Figure 1 - Portal of the European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP)

Case Study: BIM-Based Toolkit for Efficient Renovation in Buildings (BIM4EEB)

[BIM4EEB](#) is a €7 million project designed to enhance the renovation industry by developing a robust and appealing BIM management system. The project delivers a BIM-based toolset designed to assist designers during the planning and design phases, streamline construction processes for construction companies, and enable service companies to provide attractive solutions for building retrofitting.

The BIM management system, in conjunction with the toolset, aims to streamline decision-making and asset management for both public and private owners, leveraging augmented reality and digital logbooks.

The consortium is extensive, consisting of universities, research institutes, regions, construction and engineering companies, and network associations:

The BIM4EEB project delivered an innovative BIM management system (BIM4EEB BIMMS) that includes six tools:

BIM Management System (BIMMS)

6 BIM Tools designed for building renovation

41 public reports on the project's development

22+ scientific publications available on Zenodo

55 videos on the BIM4EEB YouTube channel

and more on the BIM4EEB website

While this appears promising, the official project website primarily offers only short YouTube videos demonstrating how the tools work and what can be achieved with them. Unfortunately, the site's search function is non-functional, and there are no direct links to the developed system. A review of the 41 reports provides a hint about where to find the platform. To access the platform, one must [register](#) as a new user. However, it appears that this functionality is currently disabled.

Regrettably, this is not an isolated case. EU-funded projects' deliverable reports are typically made publicly available and research articles are discoverable on

Zenodo or other repositories. However, the actual tools developed in EU-funded projects are often not made (easily) available, and there appears to be lack of dedicated repositories for storing and cataloguing digital tools developed in EU programmes to support optimal discovery.

We could consider if digiNEB can initiate standardisation - escrow meta-databases to allow end-users to find developed and accessible tools and learning materials, formulation of conditions to be set by the EU commission to demand functional infrastructures and storage solutions of the projects to allow their results to be usable over time to a greater extent.

Links

<https://www.bim4eeb-project.eu/index.html>

<https://bim4eeb.oneteam.it/BIMMS/RegisterPage.aspx>

Figure 2 - Website of the BIM4EEB project, a year after the project was finished.

4.2 The Open-Source Community of Parametric Design

Parametric design is a design method in which features are shaped based on algorithmic processes rather than direct manipulation. Comparing the world of parametric design tools to what is produced in EU projects, a significant difference becomes evident. Grasshopper, a visual programming language and environment that operates within the Rhinoceros 3D computer-aided design (CAD) application, boasts a multitude of plugins. These plugins are well-categorized and available for download, often with opportunities for further development on repositories like GitHub as open-source projects. Typically, the developers behind these tools are individuals or small teams, overlapping with the architectural design community, consisting of young academics, architects, and small design offices. Their motivation appears to be the satisfaction derived from the adoption of their tools within the community, as evidenced by the number of downloads.

Figure 3 - Portal for parametric design: Parametric House

Case Study: Learn Visual Programming

We have added over 60 parametric design tools and projects to the DigiNEB.eu database, among which the [Learn Visual Programming](#) initiative stands out as an interesting showcase bridging tool development and training. Learn Visual Programming is a concise website featuring two toolsets: NGon - Polygonal Mesh Processing Tools and OpenNest - Tools for Digital Fabrication. Additionally, it provides a comprehensive guide for using Grasshopper in Rhinoceros. The primary objective of the site is "to provide an efficient and enjoyable learning experience for both beginners and advanced users." This is achieved through video tutorials, thorough explanations, and easy-to-follow exercises.

The site is managed by two young individuals, Petras Vestartas and Lina Vestarte, both trained as architects. Their NGon and OpenNest toolsets appear to be widely used, boasting 66,000 and 124,000 downloads, respectively.

While the educational component of their site is rather unique, the openness and extensive use of parametric design tools are not.

These tools are typically developed using the developers' own resources or income and do not appear to be funded by EU projects.

We should consider funding options for developers of widely used systems to allow them to maintain the solutions and build up their organisation to allow long-term support. In this case two people not able to continue can have a big negative impact on a NEB community in this context.

Links

<https://www.learn-visual-programming.com>

Figure 4 - Website of Learn Visual Programming.

4.3 Supporting Citizen Participation

One of the three core values of the NEB initiative is "together / inclusivity". Therefore, we have given special attention to the tools available for enabling citizens to participate in the design and planning of their own communities. We identified a few valuable databases containing a wide variety of tools to support communities and citizens, such as [Democracy Technologies](#). In this field, we observed two main groups of tools: commercial Software-as-a-Service (SAAS) platforms that require payment and store data with the developer, and a substantial open-source offering, typically developed by civic organizations or local/regional authorities.

Figure 5 - Portal for Citizen Participation: Democracy Technologies

Case Study: Digidem Lab

[Digidem Lab](https://digidemlab.org/en/) is a civic tech tool that places its focus on designing inclusive processes for citizen participation. The tool aims to involve under-represented groups and utilizes international experiences and methods to create citizen-centered processes. The platform leverages Decidim, a leading digital platform for citizen participation, to facilitate dialogues and streamline processes for local authorities. Digidem Lab also provides process development and digital tools for participatory budgets. Furthermore, it offers training in community organizing, enabling individuals to collaborate with their local communities and effect the changes they desire.

Digidem Lab, based in Göteborg, Sweden, is a cooperative owned and operated by a dedicated team committed to pioneering innovative approaches to enhance political and democratic processes. The tools used are open source. Their services encompass:

- Process development and consultation for participatory processes
- Training in democratic participation and community building
- Development and support of digital tools for participation and transparency

In this cluster of tools, a common trend emerges. Participatory tools are often developed not by large consortia or individuals or duos, but by civic organizations, municipalities, or similar entities.

Links

<https://digidemlab.org/en/>

<https://democracy-technologies.org>

Figure 6 - Website of Digidem Lab.

4.4 The wild west of AI tools

In this section of the landscape report, we delve into the realm of AI tools. It's important to note that providing a comprehensive overview of the AI tools available for architectural designers and other creatives runs the risk of becoming obsolete shortly after publication. This landscape is evolving rapidly, and currently, there are no databases dedicated to these tools.

Instead, various individuals share their experiences with AI tools on social media platforms like YouTube and Instagram through news reports. The more prominent cases receive review articles in architectural blogs. Consequently, tracking AI tools requires a different approach. However, one thing is clear: this field is highly dynamic, not very open and difficult to track.

Figure 7 - Instagram account documenting AI in architecture.

Case Study: XKool Technology

Established in 2016 by a forward-thinking team comprised of Wanyu He, a former senior architect at OMA; Chun Li, a former senior engineer at Google; and Xiaodi Yang, a distinguished cross-over designer, XKool Technology embarked on a mission with a clear goal in mind. Their aim was to liberate designers from tedious, repetitive tasks, empowering them to channel their energies into creativity and gain a competitive edge in the market. The company's journey commenced with an in-depth exploration of computational protocols. Their objective was to create a wide array of environmental scenarios by combining spatial data with legal constraints, all derived from extensive data processing. XKool recognized that this approach was made feasible in part due to China's urban planning regulations, which provided a favourable framework for developing new methodologies for replicable environmental design.

XKool now faces the challenge of adapting their methods to different regulatory environments, recognizing that the scarcity of readily available data in various contexts presents a significant obstacle to formulating computational design solutions. As an emerging startup, XKool introduced an innovative fusion of existing AI technologies. They reimagined spatial formation techniques and translated these innovative capabilities into collaborative tools. Their exclusive platform, known as Alchitect, functions as a canvas where carefully curated inputs and post-analysis observations shape the medium through which they engage with spatial complexity, effectively transforming it into a dynamic, real-time laboratory.

The XKool AI Design Cloud Platform operates as a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) solution. The product resides in the cloud, granting users access to software and hardware services through their purchased IDs. This ecosystem encompasses users, the XKool product, and their team, forming an interconnected network. Some users grant authorization to utilize the data generated during their interactions with the XKool product. Following a professional evaluation and data refinement process, this information is leveraged to enhance the quality and intelligence of XKool product models.

XKool is a spin-off of OMA, the architecture studio led by Rem Koolhaas. In this respect, it mirrors the typical development seen in a few large design firms, where former employees branch out to establish their own ventures.

Link

<https://www.xkool.ai>

Figure 8 - Website of XKool.

5. Gaps

To provide a comprehensive overview of the landscape analysis, we can create a graphical representation using two axes: openness and developer size.

Figure 9 - Positioning the digital projects/tools on two axes: openness and developer size

Horizontally, you will find the developer size, with larger Horizon Europe consortia on the left and micro-enterprises and individual developers on the right.

Vertically, you will find the level of accessibility and openness, with open-source tools listed in well-adopted repositories at the top and standalone websites lacking proper access to software output at the bottom.

Among our initial collection, Horizon Europe and AI projects appear to be the least open, while parametric tools and AI projects are in size closer to the standard architectural office. Community engagement tools and parametric design tools tend to be the most open tools.

While this simplification has its limitations, it aids in identifying gaps that need to be addressed. When considering the collection of the first 250+ identified tools, we observe the following gaps:

Gap 1: Funding

We do find digital tool development among architects, designers, and civic organizations as part of the NEB community. However, there seems to be a poor fit with EU programming. Few, if any, of these developed tools declare support from EU-funded projects. Given the predominantly micro-enterprise structure of the architectural design sector, there may be a mismatch with the complex and large calls in the Horizon programs.

Gap 2: Accessibility

While the majority of developers of parametric design tools and participatory tools for citizens have adopted the principle of open (source) software, the tools produced in EU projects are either not easily accessible or not accessible at all.

Gap 3: Findability

The field has many overviews of digital tools relevant to the NEB community, but these are dispersed across various online locations. Locating these resources and making the best use of them can be quite challenging.

Gap 4: Integration

The NEB is founded on three key principles: aesthetics, sustainability, and inclusion. While we were able to identify tools in each of these fields, integrating these tools is a different story.

6. Preliminary recommendations and next steps

The following preliminary recommendations emerge from the identified gaps:

- **SMEs and Microcompanies:** Funding options are required for developers of widely used systems to allow them to maintain the solutions. Startups and SMEs in the field should be enabled to scale more rapidly and ensure long-term maintenance to support the user community (e.g. VOLUM3 and the “Learn Visual Programming” use case)
- **Incentivise common database repositories** to allow end-users to find developed and accessible tools and learning materials. The formulation of conditions ought to be set by the European Commission demanding functional infrastructures and storage solutions of the projects and allow their results to be usable over time to a greater extent.
- Add **tools for cross-domain collaboration** that solve interoperability, e.g. VOLUM3 (3LHD); WoodLaunch (Basajaun); the OCES ontology ecosystem connecting BIM with legal, supply chain that ICF has been building with partners.
- Consider a TWG related to newly-launched **Materials Commons** for Material Passports / Advanced Materials (with ICF/BEDA).

7. Next steps

The overview of more than 250 tools and projects is provided through the DigiNEB.eu website based on a standard template, provided by the platform.

The template asks for an extensive set of data, summary texts and images that are usually available on the websites where the tools or projects are published. While most of them are developed in public programming requiring open access or published as open source, the use of web texts is ambiguous.

The sites often lack a clear rights declaration and one could question the added value of duplicating.

An alternative approach could focus on the existing repositories, to give those more exposure, reduce the info on the tools but improve the search capabilities on keywords, and offer the opportunity to host the tools. In such a way the catalogue could become a jumping board for further research, a search engine that covers multiple sources and grow into a full repository.

Despite the work that went into the documentation of the first 250 tools we should run a pilot or such an alternative approach works and would have a stronger appeal to the developers and users of digital tools.

Additional categories of project or tools that we could identify in phase 2:

- Management of infrastructures;
- biodiversity linked to a development site;
- tools that allow sources like e.g. Xeno Canto (<https://xeno-canto.org/>) to be integrated with planning tools and offer information about the preferred form/material for habitats to encourage local species;
- measuring pollution;
- Nature Based Solutions.